

DESIGNING THE SMART AND PRECISE IRRIGATION SYSTEM IN GREEN HOUSES

Mukhammad Maftun

dotorate student of Yeoju Technical Institute in Tashkent,

Isaqjonov Rustamjon

master student of National Research University-TIIAME, Tashkent

Annotation: Agricultural activities utilize around 70% of the available freshwater. This underscores the importance of responsible management, using smart agricultural water technologies. Important nutrients such as acids and minerals if arranged in a precise way can affect the both productivity and yield quality. The main objective of thesis to afford a cheap technology to control agriculture process. The result obtained show that the system performance is quite reliable and has successfully overcome quite a few shortcomings of the existing systems by reducing the power consumption, maintenance and complexity, at the same time providing a flexible and reliable form of maintaining the environment.

Keywords: precision agriculture, smart irrigation, hydroponics.

Аннотация: Сельскохозяйственная деятельность использует около 70% доступной пресной воды. Это подчеркивает важность ответственного управления с использованием интеллектуальных технологий сельскохозяйственного водоснабжения. Важные питательные вещества, такие как кислоты и минералы, при правильном распределении могут повлиять как на продуктивность, так и на качество урожая. Основная цель диссертации - предоставить дешевую технологию управления сельскохозяйственным процессом. Полученный результат показывает, что производительность системы достаточно надежна и успешно преодолено немало недостатков существующих систем за счет снижения энергопотребления, обслуживания и сложности, в то же время обеспечивая гибкую и надежную форму обслуживания среды.

Ключевые слова: точное земледелие, умное орошение, гидропоника.

Annotatsiya: Qishloq xo'jaligi faoliyati mavjud chuchuk suvning taxminan 70% dan foydalanadi. Bu aqlli qishloq xo'jaligi suv texnologiyalaridan foydalangan holda mas'uliyatli boshqaruv muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Kislotalar va minerallar kabi muhim oziq moddalar, agar aniq tartibga solingan bo'lsa, unumdorlikka ham, hosil sifatiga ham ta'sir qilishi mumkin. Dissertatsiyaning asosiy maqsadi qishloq xo'jaligi jarayonini boshqarish uchun arzon texnologiyani ta'minlash. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tizimning ishlashi ancha ishonchli va energiya sarfini kamaytirish, texnik xizmat ko'rsatish va murakkablikni kamaytirish, shu bilan birga atrof-muhitni saqlashning moslashuvchan va ishonchli shaklini ta'minlash orqali mavjud tizimlarning bir qator kamchiliklarini muvaffaqiyatli bartaraf etdi.

Kalit so'zlar: aniq qishloq xo'jaligi, aqlli sug'orish, gidroponika.

Introduction

In green houses there are a lot of parameters such as temperature, humidity and irrigation, which are very hard to monitor all of these parameters by human. And any significant changes in one climate parameter could have an adverse effect on another climate parameter as well as the development process of the plants. Therefore, continuous 24 monitoring and control of these climate factors will allow for maximum crop yield. Temperature, humidity and light intensity are the three most common climate variables that most growers generally pay attention to. The solution for all that thing and other in use android application with Arduino to monitor and control the greenhouse environment. The desire for more agricultural output develops in tandem with the world's population. The world's population is expected to reach 9 billion people in 2050, a 30% increase over today, while the number of people employed in agriculture will continue to fall. In 1900, agriculture employed 41% of the workforce; by 2000, it employed only 1.9 percent of the workforce. One of the most crucial technological developments that has permitted this is agricultural equipment.

Even while agricultural equipment has enabled previously unheard-of levels of productivity, it must continue to improve as the population expands and labor becomes scarce. Greenhouse losses must be minimized in order to become more efficient, as it is estimated

that up to 12% of a soybean crop is lost during harvest alone, and this figure can be significantly higher for other crops. Irrigation system in Green houses is one of the most important technological advancements that has enabled this. Even though agricultural equipment has enabled previously unheard-of levels of productivity, as the population grows and manpower becomes scarce, it must continue to improve. In order to become more efficient, yield losses must be avoided, as up to 12% of a soybean crop is lost during harvest alone, and this figure can be much greater for other crops. The widespread use of innovative technology is a surefire approach for Uzbekistan to progress and rise among the world's nations [1]. "Continuous development of agricultural production, further improvement of the country's food security, extending production, utilization of high-yielding agricultural machinery," according to the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021. rational use of land and water resources, introduction of modern intensive agro-technologies ”.

Materials and methods

The study compared two types of liquid fertilizer. which were an organic hydroponic fertilizer and an inorganically formulated nutrient solution. The ideal nutrient formula for basil was adapted from a hydroponic herb culture fertilizer formula recommended by Agodynamics (Anonymous. 1995).

In green houses there are a lot of parameters such as temperature, humidity and irrigation, which are very hard to monitor all of these parameters by human. And any significant changes in one climate parameter could have an adverse effect on another climate parameter as well as the development process of the plants.

Plant Tissue Analysis

Chlorophyll Analysis with a SPAD Meter. A hand held chlorophyll SPAD meter (Minolta SPAD502 Chlorophyll Meter. Spectrum Technologies Inc., Plainfield. 111.) was used to take weekly readings on two leaves of each basil plant. Therefore, a total of 74 measurements were taken on each experimental unit. Because each experimental unit was replicated three times. an average of the 72 readings from each medium/fertilizer treatment combination was used to make conclusions on the chlorophyll data.

Nitrate Nitrogen Analysis.

The procedure For collecting the nitrate data was to harvest a random sample of leaf tissue, squeeze the leaf tissue with a sap press to extract plant tissue liquid, place a couple of drops of the sap onto the meter sensor, and record the nitrate nitrogen reading. A compact ion meter (The Horiba Cardy Ion Meter, Spectrum Technologies Inc., Plainfield, Ill.) was used to measure nitrate nitrogen content. Measurements were made during the final week of each study. In the 1996 study, ten random plants were sampled for each fertilizer treatment from

the bag mix, five plants were sampled for each fertilizer treatment from the perlite, and five plants were sampled for each fertilizer treatment from the rockwool. For the 1997 study, five plants were sampled for each fertilizer treatment from each growing system.

Statistical Analyses

Fresh weights on the weekly harvest. dry weights on the weekly harvest. and weekly chlorophyll SPAD readings were analyzed by analysis of variance with a pairwise t-test on the least square means and repeated measures model. Total harvest per plant, final plant dry weight. and final plant height were analyzed with a pre-planned comparison using least square means. Significant differences between treatments were determined at a probability level of 0.05.

Conclusions and recommendations

This paper determined that *Ocimum basilicum* (sweet basil) can be successfully grown in a Yangiyul greenhouse and can be grown hydroponically and organically in a greenhouse. The physical appearance and health of the plants declined after four months of weekly

harvesting in the 1996 and 1997 studies, and the yield declined four months in to the 1996 study. The 1996 study shows a general downward trend in fresh weight and dry weight yields for all growing systems reflective of the decreasing light intensities and a reduction in photoperiod activity. The 1997 study shows an upward trend in fresh weight and dry weight quantities for all growing systems reflective of increasing light intensities and a rise in photoperiod activity.

Organoleptic taste test panel members determined with a triangle difference test that the organically fertilized plants were different from the salt-based fertilized plants for all three growing systems. Panel members also determined that no differences existed between organically fertilized and conventionally fertilized plants with regard to preference. The results reveal that there is no taste preference for plants grown with any of the four production methods tested. even though differences are distinguishable.

REFERENCES:

1. Adarsh, S, et al. “Performance Comparison of Infrared and Ultrasonic Sensors for Obstacles of Different Materials in Vehicle/Robot Navigation Applications.” IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, vol. 149, no. 1, 2016, p. 012141., doi:10.1088/1757-899X/149/1/012141.
2. Pexa M. Measurements of tractor power parameters using GPS. Research in Agricultural Engineering. 2011. V. 57. P. 1–7.
3. Makino E., Sugiyama T., Ichikawa T., Hamada K., Kawanaka M. Development of combine harvester with yield monitoring function (Part 1). Journal of JSAM. 2007. V. 69 (4). P. 79–88.
4. Akbarnia A. Study of fuel consumption in three till–age methods. Research in Agricultural Engineering. 2014. V. 60. P. 142–147.

5. Pitla S.K., Lin N., Shearer S.A., Luck J.D. (2015). Use of Controller Area Network (CAN) Data to Determine Field Efficiencies of Agricultural Machinery. Applied Engineering in Agriculture. 2015. V. 30 (6). P. 829-839.
6. Dr. P.N Modi Dr. S.M Seth. Hydraulics and Fluid Mechanics including Hydraulic Machines. Twenty first edition, 2017.